

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

UDC 547.426:621.892

MULTIFUNCTIONAL ADDITIVES FOR DIESEL FUEL

**Ayralova T.I.,
Babayev T.R.,
Aliyev A.O.**

*State University of Oil and Industry, Baku, Republic of Azerbaijan,
Baki, Azadliq 34, AZ 1010*

Abstract

In the article, ethylene glycol esters of vegetable fatty acids were synthesized in order to improve the operating qualities of diesel fuels. Ethylene glycol from cottonseed oil and KU-2 as a catalyst were used for the synthesis. Fatty acids contained in cottonseed oil enter the esterification reaction with ethylene glycol in the presence of a catalyst. At the end of the process, the monoethylene glycol ether of fatty acids was purified from other components in the reaction mixture, including diethylene glycol. Monoethylene glycol ester of fatty acid has been applied as a multifunctional additive in diesel fuels. The obtained results allowed the use of the synthesized ether as a multifunctional additive.

Keywords. multifunctional additives, diesel fuels, depressant additives, anti-smoke additives, monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acid

Introduction

One of the most important indicators of diesel fuel is its low-temperature properties. These characteristics include freezing point and cloud point, filtration coefficient and filtration temperature. By many methods, these indicators are adjusted to the requirements for winter diesel fuel. One of them is a decrease in the boiling point due to a decrease in the fractional composition of winter diesel fuel, which reduces the yield of diesel fuel due to crude oil and is a disadvantage of using this method.

Another way is to add various amounts of light oil products to winter diesel fuel. However, this reduces the ignition temperature of diesel fuel. To eliminate these shortcomings in the production of winter diesel fuel, pour point depressants are currently used. The additive can reduce the freezing point of diesel fuel by 15-20°C.

The currently known pour point depressants are classified as follows:

- copolymer of ethylene with polar monomers (copolymers of ethylene and vinyl acetate and their compositions, terpolymers based on ethylene and vinyl, copolymer of ethylene with other polar monomers);
- products of polyolefin type (ethylene-propylene copolymer, ethylene-propylene-diene and their degradation products, degradation products of α -olefins, modified polyolefins);
- polymethacrylate additives (polyalkyl(meth)acrylates, copolymers of alkyl(meth)acrylates);
- non-polymeric chemicals (alkylnaphthalene, esters of polyhydric acids and alcohols, amides, etc.) [1].

Thus, the tightening of environmental requirements for fuels and products of their combustion, the need for the full use of oil resources raises the question of finding additional sources of raw materials for the

production of new generation motor fuels and additives for oil refineries.

Combustion modifiers consist of smoke control, flame retardant additives, and combustion catalysts and are used to improve fuel combustion and reduce deposits in engine parts. It is clear that the synthesis of a multifunctional combustion modifier for reducing the amount of products of incomplete combustion of diesel engines is a very important issue [2].

Anti-smoke additives reduce black smoke emissions from diesel engine exhaust. In the combustion chamber, intensive splitting of the fuel occurs at the pre-ignition stage of combustion, as a result of which an intermediate compound is formed, which then burns out. Sometimes, for some reason, the connection cannot burn out completely. So, when the engine is running on a rich mixture (this happens in forced mode engine or in the event of a malfunction of the fuel equipment) after the piston a large amount of the mixture burns, and the heat released is used to heat the exhaust gases. Unburned particles are emitted into the atmosphere in the form of black smoke. Thus, emissions of completely unburned fuel lead to a decrease in engine efficiency.

In addition, resin particles adsorb carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons on their surface, causing environmental pollution with these substances. The main principle of action of anti-smoke additives is to ensure complete combustion of the resulting compaction products until the combustion of the bulk of the fuel in the combustion chamber [3].

There is no clear mechanism of action for anti-smoke additives. But there are two hypotheses in this regard. According to the first (based on physical effects), additives have an anticoagulant and dispersant effect on compaction particles. As a result, the particles remain intensely dispersed and burn intensively. The second hypothesis is based on the chemical effect of

these additives on the combustion of compaction particles, which also have a catalytic effect due to hydroxyl radicals.

These mechanisms may be related to certain groups of additives. In practice, rather, both mechanisms can be used. The most studied are the proposed options related to the mechanism of action of barium smoke additives. One of these options is the ability of barium compounds to gasify compaction products with hydroxyl radicals formed during the reaction with combustion products. Based on optical probing of the fuel mixture with helium and neon lasers, it was suggested that barium anti-smoke additives are deposited on particles and ensure their dispersion, thereby accelerating their combustion. Based on this mechanism of action, it can be said that, in fact, barium additives are not combustion catalysts. They are more efficient when burning heavy fuels [4].

Examples of other metal-containing ignition promoters include additives containing alkaline earth metals. A sulfate mechanism of action of these additives has been proposed. It consists in the formation of metal

sulfates from sulfur in the fuel and the subsequent adsorption of the resulting sulfates on the active centers of the compaction particles, preventing their growth.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Method for the synthesis of ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils

For the synthesis of ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil, a three-necked flask equipped with a heater, a stirrer, a thermometer, a Dean-Stark trap and a reflux condenser was loaded with a mixture consisting of weighed fatty acids (FA) and the amount of ethylene glycol corresponding to this amount for a given acid/glycol molar ratio, 100 ml of benzene (for the azeotropic extraction of water from the reaction products) and catalyst KU-2-8. After that, a mechanical stirrer, a heater were connected, and the esterification reaction was carried out at the appropriate temperature and reaction time.

The external view of the reaction unit is shown in Fig.1.1

Figure 1.1 External view of the reaction plant.

1 - mixer; 2 - holder; 3 - flask shutter; 4 - thermometer;
5 - flask; 6 - heater; 7 - Dean-Stark trap; 8 - reverse refrigerator.

The reaction mixture was heated until the volume of water released in the trap remained constant for 30 min. The depth of the reaction was judged by the acid number and saponification number. After completion of the esterification process, the reaction products were poured into a separating funnel, where the esterificate was treated successively with water, 5

% solution of alkali or soda and washed again with water until neutral. After drying the solution of the resulting esters with calcined sodium or magnesium sulfate, the remaining solvent was distilled off at atmospheric pressure.

In the synthesis of monoglycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils, in the process of esterification of fatty acids with glycols, depending on the molar ratio of the initial reagents, along with monoesters, the formation

of diesters is also possible according to equations (1) and (2).

To obtain monoesters, the process must be carried out in an excess of glycol. The material balance of the process of synthesis of monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils synthesis process is given below in table. 2.1

Table 2.1.

Material balance of the ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils synthesis process

Filed		
Taken:	г	% mass.
Fatty acid	46,0	48,2
ethylene glycol	49,6	51,8
Total:	95,6	100
Received		
Ethylene glycol ethers ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils synthesis process	43,0	44,9
Water	7,6	7,8
Unreacted FAs	3,7	3,9
Return ethylene glycol	33,80	35,5
Losses	7,5	7,9
Total	95,6	100

The purity of the obtained monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil was determined using the IR spectrum (Fig. 2.1)

Rice. 2.1. IR spectrum of ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils

On the IR spectrum of monoethylene glycol ethers of ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils absorption bands of the OH group of the ethylene glycol fragment are fixed at 3438 cm⁻¹, absorption bands of C=O and C-O-C groups, respectively, at 1738 and 1172 cm⁻¹.

Physico-chemical properties of the obtained monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil are shown in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2.

Physico-chemical properties of monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil

Indicators	ethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of vegetable oils
Density at 20°C, kg/m ³	955,6
Acid number, mg KOH/g	7,3
Essential number, mg KOH/g	186
Hydroxyl number, mg KOH/g	86
Kinematic viscosity, at 20° mm ² /s	6,45
Pour point, °C	-16
Iodine number, g, I ₂ /100 g °C	73,87

Conclusions

1. Monoethylene glycol esters of cottonseed oil fatty acids, as well as glycerol triacetate (an ester of glycerol and acetic acid) were synthesized and investigated as multifunctional additives to diesel fuels.

2. It was found that monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil, as well as glycerol triacetate, can be used as a resource-enhancing additive to diesel fuels when x is added to the straight-run diesel fraction D1 in the amount of 3.0-7.0% and 2.5- 5.0% wt. respectively.

References

1. H.R. Veliev, A.G. Talybov, Kh.Sh. Teiubov, Z.M. Aliyev. Multifunctional additives for diesel fuels based on vegetable raw materials. // Abstracts of reports

for the Russian Congress on catalysis "ROSKATALIZ". Novosibirsk city. 2011. 262 p.

1. Zhifeng L., Zhang F., Zhang Q. et al. Effects of fuel components on the antistatic performance of poly(olefin sulfone)s in hydrotreated diesel. // Petroleum processing section. 2011 Vol. 27. p. 946-951.

2. Patent USA 7468539. (B2) 2010. Diesel fuel composition / Wetzel T.D

3. Demirbas A. Comparison of transesterification methods for production of biodiesel from vegetable oils and fats // Energy Conversion and Management. 2014. Vol. 49. p. 125-130

4. Berenblyum A.S., Danyushevsky V.Ya., Katsman U.A. Obtaining motor fuels from non - edible vegetable oils and fats. // Petrochemistry. 2010. v. 50(4). With. 317-323

EFFECT OF SOLVATOTHERMAL COPPER (II) NANOOXIDE ON BURNING RATE OF PYROTECHNIC COMPOSITIONS

Zhukov E.E.,

Junior Research Scientist,

Laboratory for High-Energy Compounds Synthesis

Institute for Problems of Chemical and Energetic Technologies, Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of

Sciences (IPCET SB RAS)

Biysk 659322, Russia

ORCID 0000-0002-2153-6299

Il'yasov S.G.

Dr. (Chem.), Main research scientist,

Laboratory for High-Energy Compounds Synthesis

Institute for Problems of Chemical and Energetic Technologies, Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of

Sciences (IPCET SB RAS)

Biysk 659322, Russia

ORCID 0000-0002-7853-6118

Abstract

The paper presents the results of studies on the use of the solvothermy reaction as a method of introducing nano-oxide of copper (II) onto the components of pyrotechnic compositions. The first part of the present study deals with developing a procedure for depositing nCuO onto the surfaces of KNO₃, KClO₄, Ti and B by the solvothermal method using ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate. The second part of the study involves physico-chemical characterization of the modified components (KNO₃@CuO, KClO₄@CuO, Ti@CuO, and B@CuO) and testing these substances for burning rate.

Keywords: copper (II) nanooxide, solvothermal synthesis, dinitrourea salts, pyrotechnic compositions, surface modification, burning-rate modifier.

Introduction

Copper (II) nanooxide (nCuO) holds promise as a burning-rate catalyst of energy-rich systems and is applied in the development of various pyrotechnic compositions, including thermites used in compact devices [1-3]. There are studies in the literature regarding the effect of small quantities of added nCuO on the thermal stability of fire-retardants and high-energy materials components [4-8]. The nCuO additive accelerates the burning rate of energetic materials based on nitrocellulose/triethyleneglycol/ diaminoglyoxime, and ammonium dinitramide [9, 10]. Moreover, nCuO is also being extensively employed today in the other fields of science and technology. For instance, nCuO is utilized in the realm of alternative energy sources, such as solar

energy transmission and storage systems, and in various detectors and sensors [11-13]. Antibacterial properties of this compound have come into use in biotechnology, pharma and medicine [14, 15], in addition, nCuO is used to decompose chemical warfare agent simulants [16], nCuO is also applied as a catalyst in the syntheses of various chemicals [17, 18].

However, nCuO has no widespread use due to a number of difficulties and limitations:

- first, there is an insufficiently uniform distribution of nanoparticles between other particles of the composition components during mechanical mixing [19];

- second, only a limited quantity of the nano-material can be incorporated into a composition;